

Effective Counselling and Parenting: Panacea for Total Development of an Adolescent Child in Nigeria

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Abstract

In terms of encouraging self-direction, social integration, emotional growth, and intellectual development, parental involvement through positive parenting is the most significant impact in a child's total development. Adolescent's well-being in the areas of mental health, personality development, psychosocial growth, and adaptive behaviour in society are all predicted by parental role modeling, which also creates an emotional environment that is conducive to good parent-child relationships. This paper examined effective counselling and parenting: panacea for total development of an adolescent child in Nigeria. The article discussed concepts of counselling and parenting. It addressed different parenting styles and compared them with positive parenting. The paper further highlighted obstacles to positive parenting, implication for professional counselling and recommendations.

Keyword: Counselling, Positive Parenting, Parenting Styles, Adolescents

Introduction

Character development in children happens over the course of several years rather than being something that just happens to them (Almuhajir, 2021; Atika et al., 2021). Beginning with the child's birth and development into an adult in the home environment, socializing with friends in game groups, attending school, and ending with the community (Prasanti & Fitrianti, 2018; Iltiqoyah, 2020). An important goal in the early learning process is the instillation of moral principles (Zamroni et al., 2021; Rozi & Maulidiya, 2022). Children are educated and disciplined to build character traits like responsibility, honesty, independence, etc. from an early age. The early formation of moral and ethical principles must take into account child development issues (Ramdhani et al., 2019). Today's parents face the same difficulties as always. As people face problems and implement daily routines in response to their children's demands, they grow into their parental roles and build their parenting abilities. Parental effectiveness is important in how parents behave while interacting with their kids and during the entire socialization process. Young children's care, physical protection, and physical, cognitive, and emotional growth are the parents' responsibilities. They also monitor the child's integration into society and encourage socially acceptable behaviour. The child's cognitive and psychosocial development is improved if the parents believe they are effective in their parental role (Loukia, 2019). Counselling is a beneficial profession for people of all ages: infancy, adolescence, maturity, and senescence. People of all races and walks of life have used counselling services and treatments for self-growth, self-restructuring, and self-development in families, marriages, government institutions, colleges, universities, companies, organizations, associations, and non-governmental entities. Counselling as a discipline encompasses a wide range of worldwide services to mankind, including educational, vocational, psychological, and personal information that is preventive, curative, restructuring, and generative in character (Killian, 2019). Therefore, this paper will be guided with concepts discussion such as parenting, parenting styles and obstacles to positive parenting.

Concept of Counselling

In the realm of guiding and nurturing, counseling emerges as a powerful tool that holds the key to addressing the intricate tapestry of parenting and the cultivation of character in children (Bishop, 2023). The journey of character development, a slow and steady voyage spanning years, is intricately woven by a multitude of threads, including the domestic ambiance, social interactions, and community engagement (Fiehn et al., 2023). Amidst these, parents assume a role of paramount significance, sculpting the moral compass and character foundation of their offspring. Yet, the path they tread is often laden with the challenge of harmonizing their responsibilities (O'Donnell et al., 2022). Enter counseling, a vocation that extends its helping hand across age groups, from children and adolescents to adults, ushering them through the labyrinth of personal evolution, relationship intricacies, and the trials of parenting (Lenz & Lemberger-Truelove, 2023). Its purpose is resolute—to

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provide a scaffold of support, a compass of guidance, and a treasure trove of strategies to nurture constructive parenting paradigms, efficacious communication, and the blossoming of character traits (Juffer et al., 2023). Parenting stands as a symphony of commitment, one that orchestrates a child's emotional, physical, intellectual, and societal maturation (Witte, 2022). The art of effective parenting entails a methodical approach, one that plants the seeds of positive conduct and virtuous attributes from the earliest stages (Ubaidillah & Sholih, 2023). Diverse parenting styles, spanning from the authoritative to the permissive, cast their influence on a child's emotional intelligence, cognitive development, and social growth (Nyangoya, 2022).

Positive parenting thrives on gentle corrections and nurturing support, instilling not only self-assurance but also the art of problem-solving and the bedrock of wholesome relationships (Conkbayir, 2023). However, technological advancements and economic constraints are two issues that modernity brings with it that might have an impact on parenting (Sujarwo et al., 2021). It is within this backdrop that the beacon of professional counseling shines brighter than ever. It offers the compass to parents, helping them navigate the complex waters of family dynamics, surmounting the obstacles that bar the path to fostering positivity (Diamond, 2023). The scope of counseling's impact is profound and far-reaching (Kim et al., 2023). The realm of professional counselors is akin to a gardener tending to the soil of positive parenting techniques, tilling the ground for communication to flourish between parents and children, and sowing the seeds of character development strategies (Schauss et al., 2019). The integration of family counseling programs into educational institutions, coupled with parental workshops and discussion forums, serves as a bridge that connects educators and parents in a shared purpose (Kelty & Wakabayashi, 2020). In this tapestry, counselors don the mantle of educators, imparting the wisdom of positive parenting methods and providing the resources necessary for holistic growth in the realm of children and adolescents (Estiningsih et al., 2020). Beyond this, they recognize the intricate interplay between character development, academic triumph, and parental engagement, charting the course toward effective parenting that nurtures not only robust moral values but also paves the way for academic accomplishments (Clarke, 2023).

Concept of Parenting

Parenting is a vow to invest time, money, and your best efforts in a child's emotional, physical, intellectual, and social growth. Parenting is also thought of as raising a child in a structured way so that when the child arrives at school, he or she will perceive classroom activities as enhancing what they have learned at home. This will enable the child to better transfer knowledge and skills from home to school to improve academic performance. According to NTI (2009), positive transfer that supports academic achievement is achievable when knowledge and abilities gained in one learning environment—home, which is often a child's initial learning environment—are comparable to those in another context, like a school environment. Talib, Abdullah and Mansor (2011) claims that the household because of this determines a child's degree of academic achievement in school. Parenting is the art of carrying out the duty to raise and prepare children for productive lives. Parenting is a process of raising and nurturing a kid because it is an art. Psychologists like Coleridge (2009) and Talpur, Pathan, Shah (2012) have stated as much. They continued by saying that part of parenting is taking care of your child's academic progress.

Parenting is the process of raising a kid so that he will not be deprived of his education and other fundamental rights, regardless of the severity of the national economic downturn. It entails caring the youngster without overworking him so he may grow up strong and be able to handle his academic responsibilities. According to Yang, Kim, Laroche and Lee (2014), children who are overworked are frequently observed dozing off in class due to fatigue, which is detrimental to their ability to do well academically. Relationships, communication between co-parents, and the academic ideals that are supported and encouraged by both parents in a family are prominent among the elements that affect parenting generally. The benefits of consistent parenting and the values that both parents uphold, which set clear expectations for the child's academic success and other aspects of his behaviour, are similar to those of effective communication between parents and their children (Tompsett & Toro, 2010). All of these points out that parenting entails a variety of duties, including establishing guidelines for kids to follow, providing educational materials to ensure regular attendance at school, inspiring kids, especially when their spirits are low, and developing friendships with them, among other things. Children should be exposed to character development as early as feasible (Baharun, 2017). Character development is more important in the early years. Character building in early infancy is a crucial process that builds the foundation of human personality, hence failing to do so will result in the development of a troublesome personality in later life (Tanto et al., 2019). In order to develop character, one has to practice virtues both at home and at school (Maryam, 2018; Muali et al., 2021). The primary responsibility of parents in the education of their children is to provide primary education, fundamental attitudes, and fundamental skills, including religious education, personality, manners, aesthetics, affection, a sense of security, the fundamentals of following rules, and instilling habits (Cahyono et al., 2018; Munif

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et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is the responsibility of the family to impart values and conduct via what is taught in school. To put it another way, there is a connection between what is taught at home and what is taught at school. It is critical to establish a positive relationship between the school and the parents. Arif and Pratama (2019) given that education and parental care play an important part in the development of a kid's character, if a child receives strong character education at school as well as good habits at home, the child will have a positive attitude later in life (Atika et al., 2021; Almuhajir, 2021). Since the favorable attitudes these kids currently hold will gradually evaporate if the values being taught at the school do not have support from the home environment, schools can help their pupils gain a greater initial understanding while they are in school.

Parenting styles vs Positive Parenting

According to Piko and Balázs (2012), parenting practices have been linked to several elements of children's emotional, cognitive, social, and academic skills. Parenting practices are crucial to children's development. Parenting style was described by Poduthase (2012) as the attitudes that parents have toward their children. It is a collection or system of behaviours that outlines how parents and children engage in a variety of contexts and fosters productive interactional environments. The identification, growth, and development of a child's gifts and skills, as well as being familiar with social laws and norms from the parents' point of view are just a few of the many functions that parenting style provides. According to Moreno Méndez et al. (2020), parenting styles are linked to peer issues, problematic binge drinking, and general maladjustment problems. Zuquette et al. (2019) found a similar association between problematic parenting and binge drinking (Obimakinde et al., 2019). As one of the three main parenting approaches, authoritative parenting has consistently been linked to favorable outcomes, such as "psychosocial competence... maturation, resilience, optimism, self-reliance, social competence, and self-esteem;" Kuppens&Ceulemans (2019), as opposed to authoritarian parenting's negative outcomes, such as aggression, delinquency, anxiety disorders, stress, and general adjustment issues; Adubale, 2017; (e.g., depression, anxiety; Adubale, 2017; Kuppens&Ceulemans, 2019; Moreno et al., 2020; Williams et al., 2009; Wolfradt et al., 2003). In general, punitive parenting style has detrimental effects on the mental well-being of children (Zubizarreta et al., 2019).

Parental practices in Nigeria incorporate all parenting philosophies with a focus on deference to and adherence to parental directives (Akinsola, 2011 in Killian 2014). However, a lot of parents in Nigeria go along with this need for obedient behaviour and compliance with parental directives by being receptive, loving, caring, sensitive, and engaging in a two-way discussion with their children. Teenagers in Nigeria are able to regard their parents as authoritative at times and authoritarian at other times because of the parents' dual demands for compliance and attentiveness. According to research, many Nigerian parents use authoritative and authoritarian parenting techniques as well as their hybrids (Akinsola, 2010a in Killian 2014). As a result, it is hypothesized that adolescents who experienced permissive, authoritarian, or their hybrid parenting styles will report higher levels of social and performance anxiety than adolescents who experienced authoritative parenting. According to scholarly assessments, teenagers' social anxiety scores are significantly influenced by excessive parental supervision (Siegel & Welsh, 2014). A meta-analytic evaluation found that the parenting characteristic of control had a medium impact size and was not just related to children's social anxiety (McLeod, Wood, and Weisz, 2007). This relationship is often believed to be the result of authoritarian parents teaching their children that the outside world is a dangerous place where they need always be on guard. Furthermore, this idea contends that parents who exercise excessive control over their children deprive them of the opportunity to develop independent problem-solving skills. According to Saldana, J. (2012), this causes the teenager to experience a lower feeling of personal competence, which can subsequently result in social anxiety. An adolescent who experiences parental acceptance and warmth reflects more self-confidence outside the home compared to an adolescent from a home environment where rejection/cold relationships are the norm; such adolescent will manifest unsympathetic behaviours. Killian (2014) emphasizes parent-child relationship as one of the factors that enhance the child's confidence in himself or herself in pursuit of life-achievement goals, especially in the area of career and vocational choice.

Positive parenting is using gentle corrections rather than severe penalties to deal with undesirable conduct. Instead, parents actively meet their children's emotional needs via loving relationships, which may stop a lot of undesirable behaviour before it ever starts. Caley (2022) asserts that positive parenting simply encourages parents to "catch kids doing nice" and provide reinforcement that is more positive rather than concentrating solely on inappropriate conduct. Some parents worry that positive parenting is overly idealistic, contending that if parents don't teach their children understand and respond to unpleasant emotions, they won't learn how to do so later in life, which might be detrimental. However, according to psychologists, supportive parenting may boost kids' self-esteem and provide them the skills they need to make wise decisions. Additionally, it fosters their sense of self-worth, creativity, optimism, and interpersonal skills. When parents mess up and lose their temper, it's the perfect time to apologize to their kids and show them how to deal with mistakes Caley (2022).

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Obstacles to positive parenting

According to Lykken's (1997) investigation into the reasons and treatments for ineffective parenting, the high rate of unsocialized adolescents is mostly attributable to the level of ineffective, overloaded, or sociopathic parenting they have experienced. He continues by saying that with the absence of effective conventional approaches like the socialization of children through involvement in extended-family organizations, it is not entirely unexpected that there is such a high incidence of ineffective parenting. According to Lykken (1997:129–137), communities that still use this parenting style today generate children that develop successful consciences, empathy, compassion, and group collaboration, as well as reduced levels of intramural crime. According to the hypothesis, parents may feel less confident in their abilities to have a good impact on their children's lives as a result of heightened emotional anguish brought on by higher levels of economic strain brought on by reduced family income and uncertain employment situations. Any perceived or actual social-emotional support from friends or family tended to lessen the psychological consequences of these financial demands. Further, confident parents engage in numerous collaborative activities with their kids both inside and outside the house, according to Elder et al. (1995). In her article on reflective parenting, O'Brien (1996:238) makes the argument that parenting is such an important aspect of our children's lives that it must be properly planned and carried out. It is important to go back on one's reactions to assess if they were the most suitable in the given conditions and whether they best met the requirements of the kid. However, this capacity depends on the life lessons parents have learned throughout their lives as well as the parenting they have personally experienced. As a result, their capacity to satisfy the emotional and developmental requirements of their kid as well as to offer proper childcare will be greatly influenced by the quality of their own nurturing. The demands of a contemporary professional life and limited family time influence many parents. 2018 (Sanders) The 21st century demands that parents give their children, especially teenagers, a lot of their time, attention, and accessibility. However, given Nigeria's economic instability and political volatility, most parents struggle to strike a balance between job and family.

The difficulties of parenting have increased in recent years due to technical developments (such as information communication technology), social media, and media violence, which have taken time and attention away from parent-child activities and the passing on of cultural and moral values. Blondel (1998) argues that there is cause for concern if parents are unable to balance all these changes at home with respect to the values and ideas that the next generation of teenagers will adopt. The alterations that began in the previous several decades and appear irreversible, at least in the normal span, have already greatly shaped the physiognomy of the twenty-first century (Londel, 1998). Some of these advancements, like information and communications technology, are not inherently bad, but they frequently pose challenges in a variety of human endeavors, including families and homes. Ineffective communication, poor parenting, and challenging relationship patterns were all mentioned as the main problems for family connections by families. Recognizing family strengths before tackling issues might assist to strengthen connections within the family (Sanders, 2018).

The Role of Counseling in Enhancing Positive Parenting across Different Styles

Incorporating counseling into parenting practices brings positive outcomes for parents and contributes to the well-being of children (Finardi et al., 2022). Skilled counselors provide an unbiased perspective, helping parents understand their behavior and motivations (Eli et al., 2022). This self-awareness is essential for personal growth and improves parenting dynamics. Understanding fundamental principles of parenting helps parents align with their child's needs (Richards et al., 2022). Counseling offers support to parents facing challenges (Shepherd et al., 2020). Parenting can be confusing, but professionals offer guidance that validates efforts (Siverns & Morgan 2019). Counselors guide parents through conflicts, behavior issues, and emotions (Goldberg et al., 2021). They provide strategies that enhance discipline and empathy, building trust between parents and children (James et al., 2020). It is important to note that counseling is not one-size-fits-all. Families have unique needs, and counselors adapt their advice accordingly (Tokatly et al., 2021). This personalized approach increases the chances of positive change for parents. Counseling complements various parenting styles, helping parents create nurturing environments that foster their children's growth (Blewitt et al., 2021). Recognizing the value of counseling inspires parents to be proactive in nurturing their children's development (Suri & Chandra, 2021).

Implication for Professional Counselling

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The relationship between the counsellor and the counsellee during counselling is supportive. It attempts to aid students in making a suitable adjustment to the curriculum by assisting them in resolving issues that hamper their academic success, whether they arise at home or at school. Thus, if schoolchildren want to achieve in their studies, professional counselling services must be disregarded. This supports Adewuyi's (2009) claim that professional counselling include consultation, debate, deliberation, exchange of values, and assisting to modify circumstances that are preserving people's issues by encouraging self-awareness in the individuals involved. A professional counsellor's duty in the school system to effectively enhance excellent performance in learners includes assisting parents of school children to understand how exploitative most of the parenting techniques that exist in their various homes are (Nwazor, 2006), the need to adopt positive parenting (technique), and what positive parenting entails in order to facilitate excellent academic performance in children. The pursuit of academic excellence is stated in the Nigeria National Policy on Education (2004:51) as "Educational services assist the implementation of educational policy, the achievement of policy objectives, and the advancement of educational system effectiveness." This is consistent with Anagbogu (2004), Onwuasanya and Okeke (2008), who stated in their various studies that the role of professional counselling in a school whose students perform poorly cannot be overstated. This means that when an effective professional counsellor is able to counsel with the parents of the students and uses his expertise to treat the students whose behavioural problems emanate from the home, using appropriate behaviour modification techniques, both the students and the parents benefit. Silsby (2012) identified issues such as low school attendance, lack of attention, negative self-concept, lesson inattentiveness, and unequal performance. Furthermore, Castaldi (2007) observed that a lack of school-based-family therapy is shown when a student's academic performance is low owing to parental and guardian failures. All of this implies the employment of proactive counselling strategies, such as school-based-family counselling and behaviour modification programs, parent fora, and others, to assist parents in adopting good parenting in their homes, aided by the home-visit strategy. School-based family therapy is a type of therapeutic strategy that relies on the guidance and information provided by a professional therapist who specializes in family difficulties. In order to reinforce positive change in the child, the professional counsellor integrates school counselling models to solve problems that affect a child's academic performance. Part of it is a home visit in which the counsellor goes into a counselling relationship with the parents at their home or workplace to discuss ideas on how to best assist a child in his academics. It enables parents to actively participate in any wise decisions and selections that their children are assisted in making with the school counsellor to ensure positive academic performance, such as decisions against tardiness, truancy, non-payment or late payment of school fees, lack of concentration, and others (Nwaoba, 2011). These techniques might be utilized to assist a child whose parents or guardians physically abuse him or her through overwork, child leasing, kidnapping, and other means that impair his or her success in school.

A professional counsellor may be able to impart knowledge by setting up parent forums at PTA meetings and open days at the school (Haruna, 2015). This will encourage parents to embrace excellent parenting practices and will provide them with the necessary motivation. Family counselling in schools includes instruction on family life. Through oral presentations, videos of positive parents and their kids, or speeches from invited resource people, a professional counsellor utilizes his expert knowledge to drill parents on the program of positive parenting/technique and to issue a clarion cry for its adoption in families. The professional counsellor also works with schoolchildren to promote positive behavioural change to ensure improved academic achievement utilizing behaviour modification programs that are therapeutic in nature, all the while using his knowledge to assist parents in adopting good parenting.

Conclusion

Children's character development requires a continuous and consistent procedure. Counsellors must collaborate closely with parents in order to support them as they build the character of their children via effective parenting initiatives. Establishing a link between the attitudes of kids at home and their behaviour at school. In order to include parents as partners in their children's education, schools get in touch with parents via parenting programs. As a result, parents may maximize their ability to affect how their kids turn out. By overseeing parental activities, schools may work with families to create and foster a sense of early childhood.

Recommendations

1. It is advised for counsellors to start family counselling programs at schools.
2. The necessity to embrace positive parenting (techniques) in raising children in homes should be the main topic of counsellors' lectures during PTA meetings and open days at schools. In other words, counsellors should step up their efforts to provide parents with enough knowledge on the kind of parenting that promotes children's exceptional academic success.

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3. Governments (federal and state), non-governmental groups, and school authorities should consider supporting school counsellors so they may sometimes hold successful parent forums, workshops, and seminars on good parenting (method) at schools. They should provide enough money so that counsellors may buy the right teaching aids, including TVs, videos, posters, and other things, to really drive home the link between good parenting (method) and children's academic achievement.
4. Professional counsellors ought to be assigned to schools and given full practicing rights.
5. Instead of being limited to family counselling, the training program for professionals in counselling should be varied to include skills in school-based "family counselling for all counselling specializations."
6. Some school disciplines and courses, including social studies, health education, and civic education, should incorporate positive parenting.

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